

Task 4.4A: Evaluate and improve metadata quality and reusability

Technical Report

Owner: Stanford University

Revision History

Date (YYYY-MM-DD)	Version Number	Next revision due	Revision Reviewed / Approved By	Brief Description of Change
Oct 17, 2024	v1		Document created by Attila L. Egyedi (egyedia@stanford.edu), from the Stanford University Team.	Document created and shared with the Data Hub Partners
Oct 28, 2024	v2		Reviewed by Marcos Martinez-Romero (marcosmr@stanford.edu), from the Stanford University Team	Added sections for all subtasks of 4.4A, restructured some sections, and described the impact of the work done for the RADx Data Hub.

Purpose

The purpose of task 4.4A is to implement features and enhancements to evaluate, refine, repair, and augment RADx Data Hub metadata, including the following features::

1. Add support for compact metadata formats such as YAML to increase downstream consumption by the research community.
2. Develop methods to evaluate and report on metadata quality.
3. Implement external-authority validation for metadata values (e.g., ORCID validation, ROR validation).
4. Update and extend the RADx Data Hub metadata schema.
5. Develop methods to expand existing RADx Data Hub metadata.
6. Develop a viewer for RADx Data Hub data dictionaries.

This document outlines the work completed for each subtask. Each feature is accompanied by documentation summarizing the task and includes links to the relevant GitHub sources.

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4.4A(1): Add support for compact metadata formats such as YAML to increase downstream consumption by research communities

Introduction

Task A4.4 aims to enhance the accessibility and usability of metadata by adding support for compact formats like YAML. This will increase the potential for broader adoption and downstream consumption by research communities. This report outlines the technical developments and strategies implemented to achieve this goal

Task A4.4 focuses on improving the integration and consumption of metadata by introducing support for compact formats such as YAML. To achieve this, we implemented a dual approach: we developed a Java library to handle the YAML format in our backend services, ensuring efficient processing and conversion. In addition, we created a TypeScript library capable of generating the same YAML format, which is used in the user interface but can also be applied in server-side environments or Node.js projects when needed. This dual development ensures flexibility and broader adoption of the format across different platforms. The following sections detail the technical implementation of these solutions.

Problem Description

Expanding Metadata Format Support

Task A4.4 addresses the need for broader metadata format support in our system, which has historically been limited to JSON Schema and JSON-LD serialization formats. While these formats are powerful, they are often verbose and not easily consumed by all downstream users, particularly in research communities where compact, human-readable formats like YAML are preferred.

The challenge was to expand the system's capability by adding support for YAML, enabling the system to handle metadata in a more concise format. By supporting YAML alongside JSON Schema and JSON-LD, the system becomes more versatile, meeting the needs of users who require different serialization formats for their workflows.

To implement this, we developed two CEDAR libraries: one in Java for the backend services, and another in TypeScript for the frontend interface. These libraries enable seamless YAML serialization while maintaining compatibility with the existing JSON-based formats. This dual development ensures that YAML metadata can be generated, processed, and consumed across both frontend and backend systems.

Solution

The solution involved adding YAML support to the system's metadata serialization capabilities, ensuring that metadata can now be extracted from the system both in JSON and YAML format. This was achieved by developing two key libraries, one for the backend and one for the frontend, which handle the YAML format in conjunction with the existing JSON serialization methods.

The Java Library

The Java library was developed for backend services, where it handles the generation, parsing, and management of metadata in YAML format. This library integrates with the system's existing infrastructure to ensure that YAML serialization is seamlessly supported alongside JSON format. Metadata can now be downloaded in YAML taking advantage of the content negotiation feature offered by the HTTP protocol.

The TypeScript Library

In parallel, a TypeScript library was created to provide YAML serialization in the frontend interface. This library allows users to generate and interact with YAML-formatted metadata directly from the user interface, alongside the existing JSON options. Additionally, the TypeScript library is designed to be flexible, so it can

be used in server-side environments or Node.js projects, providing broad applicability.

Both libraries ensure that YAML metadata is generated consistently across frontend and backend components, aligning with the same structures and schemas used in the existing JSON formats. This consistency enables users to switch between formats as needed without disrupting their workflows.

Integration

Integration into Backend Services

The Java library was integrated into the backend services to enable seamless handling of YAML metadata. A new “download” endpoint was added supporting content negotiation, providing three formats: JSON, YAML and Compact YAML. The third format hides the provenance information from the artifacts, resulting in an even more compact serialization.

Figure 1. Context menu with download options

Integration into the User Interface

The TypeScript library was integrated into the frontend user interface to allow users to view and copy the artifacts in YAML format. The TypeScript library's modular

design allows it to be used in various environments, including Node.js, providing flexibility beyond just the frontend.


```
type: "template"
name: "Template"
id: "https://repo.metadatacenter.orgx/templates/e51e33f7-68cb-44fa-9d6c-f83e60915852"
status: "draft"
version: "0.0.1"
modelVersion: "1.6.0"
createdOn: "2024-09-26T14:35:18-07:00"
createdBy: "https://metadatacenter.org/users/68d898fd-2b81-492c-b68c-a80c8283fd8a"
modifiedOn: "2024-09-26T14:35:18-07:00"
modifiedBy: "https://metadatacenter.org/users/68d898fd-2b81-492c-b68c-a80c8283fd8a"
children:
  - key: "Element in template"
    type: "text-field"
    name: "Element in template"
    description: "Help Text"
    id: "https://repo.metadatacenter.orgx/template-fields/b731268b-b5bc-45bc-b591-f75d30e830f3"
    modelVersion: "1.6.0"
    createdOn: "2024-09-26T14:35:18-07:00"
    createdBy: "https://metadatacenter.org/users/68d898fd-2b81-492c-b68c-a80c8283fd8a"
    modifiedOn: "2024-09-26T14:35:18-07:00"
    modifiedBy: "https://metadatacenter.org/users/68d898fd-2b81-492c-b68c-a80c8283fd8a"
    configuration:
      propertyIri: "https://schema.metadatacenter.orgx/properties/3a4eb1b8-62b6-4414-8e08-6fbd16d1"
```

Figure 2. YAML serialization of a template in the editor

System Impact

By adding YAML support to the CEDAR system alongside JSON Schema and JSON-LD, the system becomes more adaptable to different use cases and user preferences. Users can now choose the serialization format that best fits their workflow, whether they need the structure of JSON or the simplicity and readability of YAML. This enhancement increases the system's overall utility and accessibility, making it a more valuable tool for diverse user groups.

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Study Documents

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Document	Document Name	File Size	Download
Study Documentation	phs002660_Project 14_Protocol.pdf	215.25 KB	
README	project14_README.html	281.40 KB	

Data Files

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Total Files: 6 Data Files: 2 Metadata Files: 2 Dictionary Files: 2

File Name	File Type	File Format(s)	# of Records	# of Variables	Metadata	Dictionary
project14_DATA_origcopy.csv	Tabular Data - Non-harmonized	csv	5102	198		
project14_DATA_transformcopy.csv	Tabular Data - Harmonized	csv	5102	188		

Note: A tooltip for the first row's Metadata column shows "Download Metadata File (320.81 KB)".

Figure 3. RADx Data Hub study page. The screenshot highlights the link for downloading metadata in JSON-LD format. We are currently enhancing the system to allow users to download metadata in YAML format.

We are now enhancing the RADx Data Hub user interface to allow users to download metadata in YAML format (see Figure 3), which offers a more human-readable alternative to JSON-LD. While JSON-LD provides rich semantic structure, it can be more complex and harder to interpret at a glance. YAML, on the other hand, is designed for simplicity and readability, making it easier for RADx Data Hub users to quickly understand and modify metadata, especially for those who prefer a cleaner, less technical format. This improvement caters to a broader range of users, particularly those looking for a more accessible and streamlined way to interact with metadata.

Resources

The code changes introduced by this task span across several GitHub repositories, including:

- Java Library:
 - <https://github.com/metadatacenter/cedar-artifact-library>
- TypeScript Library:
 - <https://github.com/project-frontend/typescript-yaml-library>
- Frontend integration:
 - <https://github.com/metadatacenter/cedar-template-editor>
- Backend integration:
 - <https://github.com/metadatacenter/cedar-resource-server>

4.4A(2): Develop methods to evaluate and report on metadata quality

This task is on track for completion by the due date of 01/31/2025.

4.4A(3): Implement external-authority validation for metadata values

This task is on track for completion by the due date of 02/28/2025.

4.4A(4): Update and extend the RADx Data Hub metadata schema

This task is on track for completion by the due date of 06/30/2025.

4.4A(5): Develop methods to expand existing RADx Data Hub metadata

This task is on track for completion by the due date of 08/31/2025.

4.4A(6): Develop a viewer for RADx Data Hub data dictionaries

This task is on track for completion by the due date of 09/30/2025.